

Post-Surgical Functional Status with Ethibond in Acromioclavicular Dislocation in Adults in a Second-Level Hospital

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ABSTRACT

Background: Acromioclavicular dislocation is a common shoulder injury. It accounts for 9% of acute shoulder injuries, with 40% of these resulting from sports and the remainder from accidents. These injuries are classified into six grades, with surgical treatment indicated starting from grade III.

Objective: To analyze the postoperative functional status using the Ethibond procedure in adults with acromioclavicular dislocation at a secondary-level hospital during 2024-2025.

Materials and methods: An observational, cross-sectional, descriptive, ambispective, and ambispective study was conducted on 87 patients with medical records from 2024-2025. The QuickDASH (Disabilities of the Arm, Shoulder and Hand) functional assessment questionnaire was administered, with a high Cronbach's alpha value (>0.95). For statistical analysis, Fisher's exact test was used to verify the normality of the data distribution. Pearson's chi-squared test (χ^2) and Cramer's V were used to assess association and correlation, considering a p-value <0.05 as significant. The sample was a convenience sample taken between 2024 and 2025. Results: At 10 weeks, 62% (52 patients) showed excellent functional status according to the QuickDASH questionnaire. An association was found between the severity of the injury and functional status, with $p = 0.011 < 0.05$. There is a statistically significant association. Cramer's V value of 0.28 indicates a moderate strength of association.

Conclusions: We conclude that the postoperative functional status is excellent with the use of Ethibond in Grade III and Grade V acromioclavicular dislocations; therefore, the alternative hypothesis is accepted.

KEYWORDS: Open reduction, Ethibond suture, acromioclavicular dislocation, functionality, clinical response, DASH.

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INTRODUCTION

Acromioclavicular dislocation is a usually traumatic injury of the acromioclavicular joint where there is damage to its connective tissues—the joint capsule and the coracoclavicular ligaments—with separation of the articular surfaces, where the acromial end of the clavicle ascends to a level superior to that of the acromion. These injuries represent

9% of shoulder injuries worldwide and increase to 40% in athletes. The injury is due to a direct fall onto the shoulder; they occur during sports activities or in traffic accidents.

Of all the joints, the acromioclavicular joint has the highest rate of injuries, accounting for approximately 45-65% of all dislocations. These injuries are due to workplace accidents or direct falls onto the shoulder in adduction. Dislocations can

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become chronic when diagnosed late or conservative treatment fails, that is, within 3 weeks of the trauma, as the soft tissues of the joint and the torn ligaments exhibit fibrosis and retraction, thus reducing their capacity for repair.

Currently, we use the Rockwood classification, which is divided into 6 grades. Grades I and II are managed conservatively, grades III and V are frequent and are managed surgically, as are grades IV and VI, although they are not commonly seen. In our hospital unit, we have been performing modified acromioplasty with Ethibond sutures for approximately five years. We use the surgical approaches described in the literature, with the difference being that we modify the suture entry site by perforating the coracoid process to create a pulley system. Currently, complications and sequelae from this surgical procedure are very rare. Therefore, this study aims to demonstrate the postoperative functional status at 10 weeks with completed rehabilitation. This research emphasizes optimizing institutional resources, as we use high-strength, low-cost sutures that result in a shorter recovery time for the working population in our study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to international ethical standards, institutional guidelines, and the provisions of the General Health Law regarding scientific experimentation on human subjects, specifically Articles 13, 16, and 20, and the 1964 Declaration of Helsinki, which states that the primary purpose of medical research involving human subjects is to understand the causes, evolution, and effects of diseases and to improve preventive, diagnostic, and therapeutic interventions.

Study Design

This was an observational, cross-sectional, descriptive, ambispective, and ambispective study conducted between January 2024 and July 2025 at Regional General Hospital No. 1 in Orizaba, Veracruz.

Population and Sample

Population registered at Regional General Hospital No. 1 of Orizaba, aged 20-60 years, with grade 3 and 5 acromioclavicular dislocation who underwent open reduction with Ethibond suture.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 20-60 years with Rockwood III and V acromioclavicular dislocation
- Open acromioplasty with Ethibond suture

- Completion of postoperative rehabilitation

Exclusion Criteria

- Rockwood I, II, IV, and VI acromioclavicular dislocation
- Lack of postoperative rehabilitation
- Failure to adhere to immediate postoperative recommendations
- Other surgical treatment: with hook plate, Mumford procedure (only), open vs. closed reduction with Kirschner wire/Steinmann pin (only)

Elimination Criteria

- Medical records lacking a percentage of information equal to or greater than the minimum required
- Conservative treatment
- Loss of function in the affected limb prior to injury
- Patients with previous amputation or disarticulation

Measurement instrument

The QuickDASH (Disabilities of the Arm, Shoulder and Hand) functional questionnaire was administered, with a high Cronbach's alpha value (>0.95).

Functional classification:

- 0–20: Excellent function
- 21–39: Good function
- 40–59: Fair function
- ≥60: Poor function

Procedure

1. Open reduction with Ethibond sutures is performed on patients with Grade III and Grade V acromioclavicular dislocations.
2. Re-evaluation is performed 10 weeks post-surgery through the outpatient Orthopedics and Rehabilitation clinic.
3. A re-evaluation is performed at 10 weeks using the Quick DASH functional scale, categorizing each patient.

Statistical Analysis

SPSS v25 was used. The following tests were applied:

- Pearson's chi-squared test for categorical variables.
- $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

In this study, the total sample consisted of 87 patients. Of these, 81 (93%) were male and 6 (7%) were female. 34 (39%) patients were in the 20-30 age group, 25 (29%) in the 31-40 age group, 15 (17%) in the 41-50 age group, and 13 (15%) in the 51-60 age group.

Table 1. Sex and age of patients with acromioclavicular dislocation

Variable	Frequen cy	Porcenta ge
Male	81	93.0
Female	6	7.0
Total	87	100

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Males predominated with 81 (93%) and the 20-30 age group with 34 (65%) n=87	34	39.0
20-30 years old		
31-40 years old	25	29.0
41-50 years old	15	17.0
51-60 years old	13	15.0
Total	87	100

Males predominated with 81 (93%) and the 20-30 age group with 34 (65%) n=87

Of the 87 patients studied, 52 (60%) patients suffered an acromioclavicular dislocation on the left side and 35 (40%) patients suffered on the right side.

Table 2. Affected side of patients with acromioclavicular dislocation

Affected Side	Frequency	Percentage
Left	52	60
Right	35	40
Total	87	100

Predominance 52 (60%) patients suffered the injury on the left side.

De los 87 pacientes totales, 63 (72%) de los pacientes sufrieron una luxación acromioclavicular grado III, mientras 24 (28%) sufrieron una luxación acromioclavicular grado V.

Table 3. Degree of acromioclavicular dislocation according to the Rockwood classification

Rockwood	Frequency	Percentage
Grade III	63	72
Grade V	24	28
Total	87	100

Grade III acromioclavicular dislocation predominated with 63 (72%) patients n=87

Of the 87 patients, 85 (98%) of the patients had no post-surgical complications, while 2 (2%) patients had some post-surgical eventuality such as exposure of the suture material and surgical site infection.

Table 4. Post-surgical complications in patients with acromioclavicular dislocation

Post surgical complications	Frequency	Percentage
Si	2	2
No	85	98
Total	87	100

85 (98%) of the patients had no post-surgical complications. n=87.

The functional status results according to the QuickDASH questionnaire showed that 54 (62%) of the patients had an excellent functional outcome, 28 (32%) had a good functional outcome, 4 (5%) had a fair outcome, and 1 (1%) patient had a poor functional outcome.

Table 5. Functional status of patients, according to the QuickDASH questionnaire

QuickDASH	Frequency	Percentage
Bad	1	1
Regular	4	5
Good	28	32
Excellent	54	62
Total	87	100

Of the 87 patients, 54 (62%) are in excellent functional condition after surgery. n=87

It was found that 34 (39%) patients no longer presented shoulder pain, 41 (47%) continued to have slight pain, and 12 (14%) had moderate pain. Regarding muscle strength, 38 (44%) patients had a Daniels scale score of 5, 46 (53%) patients had a Daniels scale score of 3, and 3 (3%) patients had a Daniels scale score of 3. Regarding limitations in performing recreational and work activities, 39 (45%) patients had no difficulty performing them, 46 (53%) had slight difficulty, and 2% had moderate difficulty performing their activities. Shoulder arcometry was above 150 degrees in 37 (43%) patients, between 120 and 150 degrees in 43 (49%) patients, between 90 and 120 degrees in 6 (7%) patients, and between 45 and 90 degrees in 1 (1%) patient.

Table 6. Post-surgical functional status in patients with acromioclavicular dislocation

	NONE		LITTLE PAIN		MODERATE PAIN		MUCH DOLOR		EXTREME PAIN		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
Shoulder pain	34	39	41	47	12	14	0	0	0	0	
	DANIELS 5		DANIELS 4		DANIELS 3		DANIELS 2		DANIELS 1		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
Muscle Strenght	38	44	46	53	3	3	0	0	0	0	
	WITHOUT DIFFICULTY		EASY		MODERATE DIFFICULTY		SEVERE DIFFICULTY		UNABLE		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
Limitation to peform work / sports	39	45	46	53	2	2	0	0	0	0	
	>150°		120-150°		90-120°		45-90°		30-45°		
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	
Shoulder measurement	arc	37	43%	43	49%	6	7%	1	1%	0	0%

Of the 87 patients, 34 patients (39%) have no shoulder pain, 38 patients (44%) have preserved muscle strength, 39 patients (45%) have no limitation to perform sports or work activities, and 37 patients (43%) maintain normal shoulder arcuation.

According to the Rockwood classification of acromioclavicular injuries, 46 patients (53%) with grade III injuries had excellent functional status, while 16 patients (18%) had good functional status. Regarding Rockwood V injuries, which are more severe, 8 patients (9%) had excellent functional status and 12 patients (13%) had good functional status. When associating Rockwood injury grade with functional status after surgical treatment, the chi-square value was 6.47 with a p-value of 0.01, considered statistically significant.

Clinically, this suggests that patients with grade III injuries tend to achieve excellent results more frequently, while those with grade V injuries show a more balanced distribution between "good" and "excellent" outcomes.

Table 7. Rockwood injury grade and functional status

Rockwood	Shoulder Functional status		Association	
	Good	Excellent	Chi cuadrada de Pearson	Cramer V
Grade III	16	46	X²: 6.47	0.28
Grade V	12	8	p= 0.011	

Since $p = 0.011 < 0.05$, there is a statistically significant association. Cramer's V value = 0.28 indicates a moderate strength of association.

DISCUSSION

Acromioclavicular dislocations are a common shoulder pathology, particularly in young and active patients, with Rockwood type III injuries being the most frequently reported in the literature (Haugaard et al., 2024). In their prospective cohort study conducted in a Danish urban population, the authors observed that this type of injury constituted 43% (x2: 507.8, p: 0.001) of cases, reaffirming its high incidence in the sports setting.

Jeong and Chun (2024), in the clinical study "Acute treatment of acromioclavicular dislocations" conducted in 50 patients in South Korea, maintain that surgical fixation in high-grade injuries provides a more stable long-term recovery. (x2:8.12, p: 0.004)

In the article "Functional Study in Patients with Rockwood III and V Acromioclavicular Dislocation Treated with the Endobutton Technique" (Sharman, 2025, India), a study of 30 patients assessing shoulder function reports that within 3-4 months, patients anatomically restore the acromioclavicular joint and achieve excellent functional status.

Kumar, 2025, India. In his article "Functional Evaluation in Acromioclavicular Dislocations Treated with Double Endobutton," the aforementioned technique was performed on 34 patients. Functionality and symptoms were evaluated at 6 and 12 weeks post-surgery, concluding that, according to the DASH scale, patients recovered excellent functionality with minimal complications and a short-term recovery.

Bruchmann in Argentina 2025, in his study "Comparison of functional and radiological results in patients with grade V acromioclavicular dislocation: overcorrection versus anatomical correction with arthroscopic stabilization," analyzed 23 patients, of whom 9 with grade V injuries continued to experience persistent pain. However, they were able to return to their daily activities without limiting shoulder function. Regarding rehabilitation, LeVasseur et al. (2021), in a US clinical study, highlighted the importance of progressive physical therapy for regaining mobility and strength, achieving comparable results between surgically treated patients (x2: 3.72, p: 0.054). Comparing these findings with the data presented in Table 6 on the association of functional status with the Rockwood classification confirms that patients with grade V injuries treated with open and closed techniques continue to experience pain, but it does not

limit function. Furthermore, regarding functional outcomes in both treatments—the proposed one and the one described in the articles—effective recovery occurs in the short and medium term. This finding is supported by statistical analysis, where the association is highly significant ($p = 0.011$), with a Cramer's V of 0.28, indicating a moderate relationship.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrated that surgical treatment of acromioclavicular dislocation with Ethibond sutures offers satisfactory functional results in the majority of adult patients operated on at Regional General Hospital No. 1 in Orizaba during the period 2024–2025. The application of this technique, inspired by the TightRope system but adapted to institutional resources, allowed for adequate joint reduction and early functional recovery, evidenced by 62% of patients with excellent results and 32% with good results according to the QuickDASH questionnaire.

The statistically significant association between the Rockwood classification and functional status ($p = 0.011$) confirms that, even in more severe cases, modified acromioclavicular reconstruction with Ethibond sutures maintains stability and Shoulder function was restored with minimal postoperative complications, with only 2% of minor adverse events reported.

These findings support the efficacy and feasibility of this technique as a cost-effective, reproducible, and low-risk alternative, especially in secondary-level hospitals where modern suspension devices are unavailable. Furthermore, the importance of adherence to postoperative rehabilitation and functional clinical follow-up using validated instruments such as QuickDASH is highlighted to ensure optimal results. Finally, it is concluded that Ethibond suture surgery represents a safe and efficient therapeutic option for the management of grade III and V acromioclavicular dislocations, significantly contributing to improved quality of life and return to work for patients of working age.

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